

FAMILY PLANNING NEEDS OF PERSONS WITH HEARING IMPAIRMENT IN IBADAN AND OSOGBO, NIGERIA

¹John Abdulrahman Imaledo, ^{1,2}Oyedunni Sola Arulogun, ²Musibau A. Titiloye

¹Department of Public Health, Chrisland University, Abeokuta, Nigeria

²Department of Health Promotion and Education, Faculty of Public Health, College of Medicine, University of Ibadan, Ibadan, Nigeria

***Corresponding author:** hisgracejohn@gmail.com

Tel: +2348067083131

ORCID ID: <https://orcid.org/0000-0002-2043-4258>

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Abstract

Objective: This study assessed the family planning (FP) needs of persons with hearing-impairment (PHI) in Ibadan and Osogbo, Nigeria.

Study design: This descriptive cross-sectional study assessed the FP needs of hearing-impaired persons in Oyo and Osun States, Nigeria.

Result: More respondents (62.2%) in Ibadan and (69.3%) in Osogbo have heard of the term MFPM. Male condom 51.2% in Ibadan and 50.0% in Osogbo and female condom (32.9% in Ibadan and 43.5% in Osogbo) topped the list of contraceptives known by respondents in both sites. More respondents (97.6% (Ibadan) and 95.4% (Osogbo) had poor knowledge of MFPM with overall mean scores of 1.02 ± 0.155 and 2.49 ± 1.57 on using a 10-point scale in both sites. More (52.4% in Ibadan and 50.9% in Osogbo) had negative perception of MFPM in both sites with the overall mean perception scores using a 10-point scale of 1.48 ± 0.50 and 5.65 ± 2.30 . More 82.9% (Ibadan) and 87.7% (Osogbo) of the participants had a positive attitude toward MFPMs with overall mean attitude scores using a 10-point scale of 14.45 ± 3.42 and 14.92 ± 3.14 at both sites. More respondents (61.8% in Ibadan and 55.9% in Osogbo) agreed that they 'ever utilized anything or made any effort to postpone/prevent getting pregnant'. More than a quarter said that they are not using any method to delay/avoid getting pregnant.

Conclusion: The results of this study show that there is an urgent need for intervention to help correct the observed gap in MFPM utilization among the study population.

Keywords: Family Planning, persons with hearing impairment, knowledge, perception

Introduction

In the recent past, family planning (FP) services have become prominent as a result of the observation that the world has witnessed an unprecedented population growth rate in the last century (Haub, 2007). A study conducted by the United Nations (UN) agency, presented a glaring picture of the global future population and its attendants' consequences (UNDESA, 2024). According to the study's, by 2050 and 2100,

the world's population would reach 9.7 billion and 10.4 billion by 2050 and 2100 respectively (UNDESA, 2020, Vollset, Goren, Yuan, et al. 2020), with more than half of the projected expansion coming from the Democratic Republic of the Congo, Egypt, Ethiopia, India, Nigeria, Pakistan, the Philippines, and the United Republic of Tanzania (UNDESA, 2020, Vollset, Goren, Yuan, et al. 2020). Evidence has confirmed that modern family planning method [MFPM] services have become the preferred method to slow population growth and reduce maternal mortality figures. However, its uptake and utilisation has remained low on the political programmes of the majority of African nations (Blanc and Tsui, 2005; Cleland, Bernstein, Ezeh, Faundes, Glasier and Innis, 2006).

In most developing countries, including Nigeria, significant progress has not been recorded in MFPM uptake (World Population Data, 2009; Ahmed, Creanga, Gillespie and Tsui, 2010; NPC and ICF International, 2019). Previous efforts to encourage the uptake of MFPM have not adequately considered the interest of people-living-with-disability (PLWD) including persons with hearing impairment (PHI) who account for over 5.0% of the world's population. The majority of these people live in low-income countries (LMICs), with restricted access to social and health services (WHO, 2013), and their reproductive/sexual health has, been neglected (WHO/UNFPA, 2009). Evidence also implies that individuals with disabilities in LMICs are more deprived than their peers without disabilities in terms of access to social supports, employment, income, and healthcare (Groce et al, 2011; WHO, 2013). As a neglected group, PLWD are hardly ever included in FP programmes, sexual reproductive health (SRH) prevention and outreach programmes (Burke, Kébé, Flink, van Reeuwijk, le May, 2017; Ganle, Baatiema, Quansah, Danso-Appiah, 2020). Information on SRH and FP is often not available in formats that are accessible to them (Wilson and Monaghan, 2006). Although PLWD have similar FP needs and SRH concerns to those without disabilities, the latter more often encounter multiple difficulties when looking for information and services because of ignorance, unfriendly attitudes, and a lack of services that are exclusively aimed at satisfying their particular needs (WHO, 2013; Wilson and Monaghan, 2006; Arulogun et al., 2013).

In Nigeria, there are more than 25 million PLWD (UNDP, 2005; WHO and World Bank, 2011), there is a lack of information concerning their FP and SRH experiences, which may be due to the fact that public health professionals have not yet considered their needs (Hughes, 2006). Although a few studies have been conducted on PHI in Nigeria (Osowole and Oladepo, 2001; Sangowawa, Owoaje, Faseru, Ebong and Adekunle, 2009), they do not offer comprehensive and accurate information, particularly relating to FP and SRH statistics. More than 3 decades after the ICPD in 1994, there is still a lack of knowledge about the most appropriate strategies to address this gap among PHI.

In fact, most researchers have linked the inability of the government and programmers to consider the social and cultural context in which individual fertility decisions and behaviour take place in Nigeria, resulting in the ineffectiveness of population policy and other interventions (Isiugo-Abanihe, 1994; Abubakar, Ibrahim et al. 2022). These interventions neglected to address the core cultural barriers to behaviour change in favour of smaller family norms (Dempsey, McAlaney and Bewick, 2018; Obono, 2003).

Note that these past efforts at addressing this issue have neglected the needs of people with special needs including PHI. This is because of the negative perception that PLWD are asexual (25). This has created a huge gap in FP service delivery to this population. Therefore, this study assessed the family planning needs of PHI in Ibadan and Osogbo, Nigeria.

Methodology

Study design

This descriptive cross-sectional study assessed the FP needs of PHI in Ibadan and Osogbo, Nigeria

Study site

The sites for this study are Ibadan and Osogbo. The two (2) sites were purposive selected out of the six (6) states capital in South Western, Nigeria and they are the administrative capitals of their respective states. Ibadan is a city situated in the southeast of Oyo State's in south-western Nigeria. It is located around 120 kilometres (75 miles) east of Nigeria's international border with the Republic of Benin and 119 kilometres (74 miles) northeast of Lagos. (Sustainable Ibadan Project, 2001). The city is covering 3,080 km² (1,190 m²) in total and it is home to the first university in Nigeria, the University of Ibadan and other higher institutions, such as the Polytechnic in Ibadan (Ogbuozobe, 2000).

Osogbo, the capital of Osun State's is also situated in the southwest of Nigeria. The city doubles as the regional administrative headquarters for the local governments of Olorunda in its north, and Egbedore to its west. The Yoruba ethnic group constitutes the majority of the population. Approximately 27.0% of the population worked as farmers as their main occupation in 1988, followed by 8.0% of traders and 30.0% of clerks and teachers. (Falade, 2000). The sites have almost the same savannah climate and cultural background. The majority of the people residing in the two sites are civil servants, farmers, and traders.

Instrument used for data collection

Both qualitative and quantitative methods were used in the data collection, including Focus Group Discussions (FGD) and In-Depth Interviews (IDI) using the appropriate FGD and IDI guides and a pre-tested semi-structured questionnaire for the quantitative data. The FGD and the IDI were used to verify the content of the questionnaire's.

Sampling Technique

Purposive sampling technique was used to select two study sites from the six states in the southwest region of Nigeria. Participants who were either married or in a relationship were randomly selected from the PHI association in the two states.

Ethical consideration

The Ethics Review Committee of the State Ministry of health, Agodi Secretariat Ibadan, reviewed and approved the proposal. The purpose of the study was made known to the respondents and verbal consent was obtained from those who agreed to participate in the study. Respondents were assured of the confidentiality, privacy, and anonymity of information provided and were given the choice not to participate in the study if they so desired, and as many that agreed were recruited for the study.

Result

Characteristics of the respondents

A total of 190 respondents were interviewed to determine the modern family planning needs of PHIs at both study sites (82 in Ibadan; 108 in Osogbo). More of them were aged between 31 and 40 years in both groups, with a mean age of 13.09 ± 9.5 in Ibadan and 37.54 ± 9.2 in Osogbo. A large majority (78.0% in Ibadan and 85.2% in Osogbo) were married in both study sites, and more (78.0% in Ibadan and 85.2% in Osogbo) were males. More than a quarter of the respondents (36.6% and 39.8% in both sites) had completed OND/NCE level of education and 86.6% and 83.3% in Ibadan and Osogbo, respectively were of the Christian faith. More participants (75.6% and 73.1% in Ibadan and Osogbo, respectively) agreed that they are currently employed. The socio-demographic data of the respondents are shown in Table 1.

Table 1. Respondents Socio-demographic Characteristics (n-190)

Variables	Ibadan n=82 Frequency (%)	Osogbo n=108 Frequency (%)
Age in years		
20 and below	1 (1.2)	0 (0)
21-30	20 (24.4)	30 (27.8)
31-40	36 (43.9)	48 (44.4)
41-50	17 (20.7)	19 (17.6)
51 years and above	8 (9.8)	11 (10.2)
Mean age	37.09 ± 9.5	37.54 ± 9.2
Marital Status		
Married	64 (78.0)	92 (85.2)
Cohabit	8 (9.8)	2 (1.9)
In a relationship but not married	10 (12.2)	14 (13.0)
Gender		
Male	39 (47.6)	73 (67.6)
Female	43 (52.4)	35 (32.4)

Level of education

No formal education	2 (2.4)	3 (2.8)
Primary school certificate	17 (20.7)	14 (13.0)
WASC/GCE	24 (29.3)	34 (31.5)
OND/NCE	30 (36.6)	43 (39.8)
HND/First degree	7 (8.5)	10 (9.3)
Above the first degree	2 (2.4)	4 (3.7)

Religion

Christianity	71 (86.6)	90 (83.3)
Islam	11 (13.4)	16 (14.8)
Traditional	0 (0)	2 (1.9)

Are you currently employed?

Yes	62 (75.6)	79 (73.1)
No	20 (24.4)	29 (26.9)

Awareness, knowledge and sources of information on family planning among respondents

More respondents (62.2% in Ibadan and 69.3% in Osogbo) have ever heard of the term MFPM (Table 2). When the respondents were asked if there was any advantage in using MFPM, 65.3% in Ibadan and 72.8% in Osogbo agreed to the statement (Table 2). In addition, 64.2% in Ibadan and 70.7% in Osogbo acknowledged knowing about any modern male FP methods (MMFPM) (Table 2). More (61.0% in Ibadan and 73.9% in Osogbo) agreed to have knowledge of any modern female FPM (MFFPM) (Table 2). Radio and TV (37.1%) topped the list of sources of information on MFPM for participants in Ibadan, while Newspapers (39.8%) topped the list of sources of information on MFPM for participants in Osogbo (Table 3).

Male condoms (51.2% in Ibadan and 50.0% in Osogbo) topped the list of male contraceptives the respondents knew in both sites (Table 3). Female condom (32.9% in Ibadan and 43.5% in Osogbo) topped the list of female contraceptives the respondents knew in both sites (Table 3). The participants' mean overall knowledge scores using a 10-point scale was 1.02 ± 0.155 and 2.49 ± 1.57 at both Ibadan and Osogbo, respectively. More respondents (97.6% (Ibadan) and 95.4% (Osogbo) had poor knowledge about MFPM (Table 4).

Table.2. Respondents' awareness of the modern family planning method

Statement		Ibadan (%)	Osogbo (%)
Respondents who have ever heard of the term MFPM	Yes	51 (62.2)	70 (69.3)
	No	31 (37.8)	31 (30.7)
	Total	82 (100.0)	101(100)
Do you believe that there are any advantages of using MFPM?	Yes	49 (65.3)	67 (72.8)
	No	26 (34.7)	25 (27.2)
	Total	75 (100)	92 (100)
Do you know of any MMFPM?	Yes	52 (64.2)	58 (70.7)
	No	29 (35.8)	24 (29.3)
	Total	81 (100)	82 (100)
Do you know of any MFFPM?	Yes	50 (61.0)	65 (73.9)
	No	32 (39.0)	23 (26.1)
	Total	82 (100.0)	88 (100)

Unprotected sex at least once	Yes	33 (40.2)	43 (50.6)
cannot cause pregnancy	No	49 (59.8)	42 (49.4)
	Total	82 (100.0)	85 (100)

Table.3. Respondents' sources of information on modern family planning methods and modern male and female family planning methods

Sources of information	Ibadan	Osogbo
	Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Newspaper	22 (26.8)	43 (39.8)
Radio and TV	26 (37.1)	27 (25.0)
Classmates and friends	21 (25.6)	17 (15.7)
Family members	9 (11.0)	10 (9.3)
Family planning professionals	15 (18.3)	15 (13.9)
Medical staff	5 (6.1)	22 (20.4)
Male family planning methods		
Condom	42 (51.2)	54 (50.0)
Vasectomy	11 (13.4)	4 (3.7)
Withdrawal	19 (23.2)	20 (18.5)
Female family planning methods		
Pills	16 (19.5)	24 (22.2)
Intrauterine device (IUCD)	5 (6.1)	8 (7.4)
Injectable (Depo-Provera)	9 (11.1)	16 (14.8)
Female Condom	27 (32.9)	47 (43.5)

Tubal ligation and female sterilization	4 (4.9)	1 (.9)
Periodic abstinence	8 (9.8)	12 (11.1)
Prolonged breastfeeding	8 (9.8)	8 (7.4)
Natural methods	5 (6.1)	5 (4.6)

*** Multiple responses**

Table.4. Respondents' overall knowledge of modern family planning method

Grouped knowledge	Variables	Ibadan	Osogbo
		Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Poor Knowledge		80 (97.6)	103 (95.4)
Good Knowledge		2 (2.4)	5 (4.6)
Total		82 (100.0)	108 (100.0)
	Mean	1.02±0.15	2.49±1.57

Results from the qualitative data

The discussants expressed several views were expressed by the discussants on the meaning and what they know about MFPM. There is a general view among them that MFPM has to do with not getting pregnant or having unwanted pregnant, none of them is aware that condom prevent sexually transmitted diseases (STD). Some of the participants said

'Conception means the plan of a man not to have too much children within his family' (Ibadan Men leader)

"Family Planning is a way of preventing pregnancies resulting in the birth of too many children and allowing for child spacing" (Osogbo Women leader)

During the FGD, the participants were asked about the modern contraceptive/family for women that they knew and how often their partner(s) used it during sexual episode with them. They, unanimously agreed that they did not know of any contraceptive for women, except for male condom as some of them said: *‘I do not know of any female contraceptive because I am not a woman and I am not married’*. (Single men in Ibadan)

‘Contraceptive/family planning is very popular these days among women and it was through the association that I came to learn the use of condoms to prevent pregnancy until you get married before you can become free from it’. (Single women in Ibadan)

Perception of respondents about family planning methods

Some questions were asked on respondents’ perception of MFPM. More (75.6% in Ibadan and 81.1% in Osogbo) agreed that MFPMs are an effective pregnancy prevention method. Moreover, 54.9% in Ibadan and 54.7% in Osogbo disagreed with the statement ‘that visiting a store to purchase condoms is uncomfortable.’ More respondents (48.8% in Ibadan) disagreed while 53.8% in Osogbo agreed with the statements that ‘Condoms are not necessary if you just have a few partners.’ Furthermore, more respondents (56.1% in Ibadan) agreed while (58.5% in Osogbo disagreed) with the statements that ‘it is unhealthy for women to use birth control pills (Table 5).

The overall mean perception scores of participants using a 10-point scale was 1.48 ± 0.50 and 5.65 ± 2.30 at both Ibadan and Osogbo, respectively. More respondents (52.4% in Ibadan and 50.9% in Osogbo) had negative perception about MFPM (Table 6).

Table.5. Perception about family planning

Statement	Ibadan n=82			Osogbo n=106		
	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Undecided (%)	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Undecided (%)
Modern FP methods are effective in preventing pregnancy	62 (75.6)	18 (22.0)	2 (2.4)	86 (81.1)	19 (17.9)	1 (0.9)
Visiting a store to purchase condoms is uncomfortable	35 (42.7)	45 (54.9)	2 (2.4)	48 (45.3)	58 (54.7)	0 (0)

Condoms are not necessary if you only have a few partners.	36 (43.9)	40 (48.8)	6 (7.3)	57 (53.8)	47 (44.3)	2 (1.9)
Use of birth control tablets is harmful for women	46 (56.1)	29 (35.4)	7 (8.5)	40 (37.7)	62 (58.5)	4 (3.8)
Condoms can be used more than once	40 (48.8)	38(46.3)	4 (4.9)	46 (43.4)	54 (50.9)	6 (5.7)
For someone like myself, purchasing condoms or other FP products would be uncomfortable.	34 (41.5)	46 (56.1)	2 (2.4)	48 (45.3)	55 (51.9)	3 (2.8)
If a woman suggested using FPMs to her partner, it would mean that she did not trust him.	31 (37.8)	50(61.0)	1 (1.2)	30 (28.3)	75 (70.8)	1 (0.9)
It would be a sign that a man did not trust his partner if he suggested she use FPMs.	32 (39.0)	48(58.5)	2 (2.4)	31(29.2)	69(65.1)	6 (5.7)
Modern FP methods reduces sexual pleasure	41 (50.0)	39(47.6)	2 (2.4)	52 (49.1)	48(45.3)	6 (5.7)
Condoms may come off the male user and vanish inside the female body.	35 (42.7)	42 (51.2)	5 (6.1)	40 (37.7)	62 (58.5)	4 (3.8)

Table 6. Respondents overall perception score of the modern family planning method

Group Perception	Variables	Ibadan	Osogbo
		Frequency (%)	Frequency (%)
Negative Perception		43 (52.4)	55 (50.9)
Positive Perception		39 (47.6)	53 (49.1)
Total		82 (100.0)	108 (100.0)
	Mean	1.48±0.50	5.65±2.30

Results from the qualitative data

They were also asked how people perceive a man who is known to be using a condom or other contraceptive. The participants showed that it is not a strange idea, and many are embracing it. The following are some of their responses:

‘Contraceptive is even more encouraged these days among people in order to help to control the number of children one will have; it is a thing that is more welcome these days and people that are using it are not seen as prostitute the way they see them in the past’ (Ibadan, Men leader)

‘Using myself as an example, they know by the number of children my wife has for me. For example, a spacing of 3 years before another pregnancy would make people aware of the FP. They would know that I prefer to prevent pregnancy’ (Ibadan, Men leader)

The leaders were also asked who decided how many children to have in the family. There are diverse views to this question. Some say, that the man (husband) should be the one making decision regarding FP, while others are of the view that the decision should be made jointly by the couples.

‘The husband chooses the number of kids and the spacing between them for the family.’ (Men leader Osogbo)

‘The mother makes the decision about the number of kids in the household if the need arises because she is the one that gets pregnant; the father can also make the decision about child spacing and pregnancy preventive measures as the man of the house, and at the end, it is better that both parents actually come together to make decisions of such contraceptive measures.’ (Women leader Osogbo)

They were also asked about their views on the reasons people want to have many children, few children, or even delay or space their children. Participants also expressed diverse views; they were of the view that people raise children these days for different reasons, unlike before. The following are some of their responses:

'People have more children to use in their businesses, to some they have few children to help them have good and proper education and those that delay children it might be due to the fact that the woman is barren or the husband has low sperm count.' (Men leader Ibadan)

'People have more children based on their own belief, especially in the olden days. People have children to use in the farm, but these days you need to caution yourself because of the economic situation. Some people, that try to delay but still come up with children they never plan for.' (Women leader Ibadan)

They were also asked how people perceive a man in their association who is known to be using condom or other contraceptive. There was a unanimous decision among the participants that it is becoming a more welcome idea and practice among couples. The following are some of their responses:

'Contraceptive is even more encouraged these days among people in order to help to control the number of children one will have; it is a thing that is more welcome these days and people that are using it are not seen as prostitute the way they see them in the past' (Ibadan, Men leader)

'Married women are in favour of FP and using contraceptives, We do encourage married women to plan their lives and know how many children they hope to have.' (Women leader Ibadan)

Discussants were also asked about their views on whether if women/men should use FP methods. Divers' views were expressed: married men in Ibadan were of the view that the women should be the only ones using contraceptives, while some were of the view that they should both agreed to use contraceptive; some of them are of the view that both the man and the woman should be involved in it, while some were of the view that it should be either as one them said:

'To me I felt the woman should be the one that should be using contraceptives since they are the one that get pregnant.' (Married men in Ibadan)

'Male should be the one using contraceptives the most since they are the one impregnating women.' This submission was supported by all the discussants (Ibadan single women).

'In my own view, women should also use it because women carry more baggage, and it may be easier for men to use it.' The whole load of pregnancy and childbirth is on the woman and she should be the one to use family planning the most'. (Married women in Osogbo)

Couple's attitudes toward modern family planning methods

Several questions were also asked to determine the attitude of the respondents' towards MFPMs. More respondents (70.7% in Ibadan and 80.6% in Osogbo) agreed with the statement that 'Pregnancy should not be allowed to occur naturally; it needs to be properly planned.' More respondents (56.1% in Ibadan agreed and 58.5% in Osogbo disagreed) with the statement that 'It is unhealthy for women to use birth control pills.' Moreover, 48.8% agreed in Ibadan and 50.9% disagreed in Osogbo to the statement that

‘Condoms can be used more than once’. Furthermore, more respondents (51.2% disagreed in Ibadan and 58.1% disagreed in Osogbo) agreed with the statement that ‘Condoms may come off the male user and vanish inside the female body’ (Table 7).

The overall mean attitude scores of participants using a 10-point scale was 14.45±3.42 and 14.92±3.14 at both the Ibadan and Osogbo, respectively. Many (82.9% (Ibadan) and 87.7% (Osogbo) had a positive attitude towards MFPMs (Table 8).

Table. 7. Couple’s attitudes toward modern family planning methods

Statement	Ibadan n=82			Osogbo n=108		
	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Undecided (%)	Agree (%)	Disagree (%)	Undecided (%)
Pregnancy must be carefully planned and, not left to happen naturally.	58 (70.7)	22 (26.8)	2 (2.4)	87 (80.6)	18 (16.6)	3 (2.8)
Husband and wife should jointly plan and talk about getting pregnant.	73 (89.0)	9 (11.0)	0 (0)	94 (87.0)	10 (9.3)	4 (3.7)
Using FPM should help prevent pregnancies that are too closely spaced.	51 (62.2)	29 (35.4)	2 (2.4)	76 (70.4)	26 (24.1)	6 (5.6)

The husband should be involved in the planning and ensure that his wife uses a contraceptive method. 64 (78.0) 18 (22.0) 0 (0) 81(75.0) 23 (21.3) 4 (3.7)

The wife should be involved in the planning process and ensure that her husband uses a contraceptive method. 59 (72.0) 22 (26.8) 1 (1.2) 87 (80.6) 17 (15.7) 4 (3.7)

Traditional contraceptive methods are less successful than modern contraceptive method. 51 (62.2) 28 (34.1) 3 (3.7) 66 (61.1) 39 (36.1) 3 (2.8)

Contraception will not interfere with a couple's ability to have a sexual relationship. 43 (52.4) 34 (41.5) 5 (6.1) 54 (50.0) 49 (45.4) 5 (4.6)

The effectiveness of a family planning programme depends on the support of the husband. 70 (85.4) 11(13.4) 1 (1.2) 95(88.0) 10 (9.3) 3 (2.8)

Wife support is crucial to the success of an FP programme	68 (82.9)	14 (17.1)	0 (0)	92 (85.2)	10 (9.3)	6 (5.6)
Only wayward women use contraceptives	38 (46.3)	39 (47.6)	5 (6.1)	44 (40.7)	59 (54.6)	5 (4.6)

Table. 8. Respondents overall attitude score of modern family planning method

Overall Attitude	Variables	Ibadan Frequency (%)	Osogbo Frequency (%)
Negative Attitude		14 (17.1)	18 (16.7)
Positive Attitude		68 (82.9)	90 (83.3)
Total		82 (100.0)	108 (100.0)
	Mean	1.83±0.38	7.31±1.98

Results from the qualitative data

Discussants were also asked about their views on whether women/men should use FP methods. Divers' views were expressed: married men in Ibadan were of the view that the women should be the only ones using contraceptives, while some were of the view that they should both agree to use contraceptive; some of them are of the view that both the man and the woman should be involved in it, while some were of the view that it should be either as one them said:

"To me I felt the woman should be the one that should be using contraceptives since they are the one that get pregnant." (Married men in Ibadan)

‘In my own view, women should also use it because women carry more baggage, and it may be easier for men to use it.’ The whole load of pregnancy and childbirth is on the woman, and she should be the one to use family planning the most.’ (Married women in Osogbo)

Modern FP methods and reasons for choice

Some questions were asked to determine their preferred MFPMs and the factors that influenced their decisions. More women (60.8% in Ibadan and 79.3% in Osogbo) were of the view that there were no traditional/cultural belief against use of contraceptive methods in their community. More women (61.8% in Ibadan and 55.9% in Osogbo) agreed that they ‘ever utilised anything or made any effort to postpone or prevent getting pregnant.’ More people (71.3% in Ibadan and 56.6% in Osogbo) are also of the view that they always use FP. More respondents (78.7% in Ibadan and 76.9% in Osogbo) also agreed that condoms topped the list of their preferred MFPMs; they also said that they preferred that both partners use their preferred FPMs (60.0% in Ibadan and 75.0% in Osogbo) (Table 9).

More of them (62.8% in Ibadan and 50.0% in Osogbo) agreed that they had ever encouraged their partner to use contraceptives. More respondents (53.7% in Ibadan and 57.1% in Osogbo) agreed that they were currently not taking any action or avoiding getting pregnant in any way with their partner/someone. Some reasons were given by respondents on what inform their contraceptive choices; these includes ‘It is convenient’ (29.3% in Ibadan and 24.5% in Osogbo) and ‘it is safer to use’ (42.7% in Ibadan and 44.3% in Osogbo). Some of the respondents (47.5% in Ibadan and 43.4% in Osogbo) said that they would like to have (more) child or children. Moreover, some of the respondents (66.7% in Ibadan and 53.8% in Osogbo) who are presently not using any FPMs agreed that they think they will use the FPM to temporarily put off or forego being pregnant at any time in the future (Table 9).

Table 9. Modern FP methods and reasons for choice

Statement	Ibadan Frequency (%)	Osogbo Frequency (%)
Traditional /cultural belief are against the use of contraceptive methods		
Yes	31 (39.2%)	19 (20.7%)
No	48 (60.8%)	73 (79.3%)
Total	79 (100%)	92 (100%)

Ever used anything or made any effort to postpone or prevent pregnancy.

Yes	47 (61.8%)	52 (55.9%)
No	29 (38.2%)	41(44.1%)
Total	76 (100%)	93 (100%)

Always use family Planning

Yes	57 (71.3%)	56 (56.6%)
No	23 (28.7%)	43 (43.4%)
Total	80 (100%)	99 (100%)

Preferred FP method

Condom	48 (78.7%)	50 (76.9%)
Withdrawal	6 (9.8%)	3 (4.6%)
Pills	0 (0%)	3 (4.6%)
Injection	7 (11.5%)	9 (13.9%)
Total	61 (100%)	65 (100%)

Prefer this method to be used by you, your partner, or both of you

Me	18 (30.0%)	8 (13.3%)
My partner	6 (10.0%)	7 (11.7%)
Both of us	36 (60.0%)	45 (75.0%)
Total	60 (100%)	60 (100%)

Ever visited the clinic for
contraceptives/family
planning?

Yes	50 (63.3%)	56 (55.4%)
No	29 (36.7%)	45 (44.6%)
Total	79 (100%)	101 (100%)

Have you ever encouraged your
wife/partner to commit an
abortion?

Yes	28 (35.9%)	18 (18.2%)
No	50 (64.1%)	81 (81.8%)
Total	78 (100%)	99 (100%)

Encourage your partner to use
contraceptives

Yes	49 (62.8%)	49 (50.0%)
No	29 (37.1%)	49 (50.0%)
Total	78 (100%)	98 (100%)

Currently taking action or
utilising any method to delay or
prevent getting pregnant with
your partner or someone else

Yes		
No	38 (46.3%)	56 (57.1%)
Total	44 (53.7%)	42 (42.9%)
	82(100%)	98 (100%)

Modern FP methods and reasons for choice Cont'd

Statement	Ibadan Frequency (%)	Osogbo Frequency (%)
Reasons for your choice of contraceptives		
It is convenient	24 (29.3%)	26 (24.5%)
It is relatively cheap	18 (22.0%)	10 (9.4%)
Availability	17 (20.7%)	17 (16.0%)
Partner preference	24 (29.3%)	20 (18.9%)
It is safer to use	35 (42.7%)	47 (44.3%)
***Multiple response		
Places where the current method can be obtained		
Pharmacy	6 (37.5%)	5 (21.7%)
Chemist/shop	2 (12.5%)	4 (17.4%)
Hospital	6 (37.5%)	12 (52.2%)
Supermarket	2 (12.5%)	0 (0%)
Social group	0 (0%)	2 (8.7%)
Total	16 (100%)	23 (100%)
Where any FP methods can be purchased in this community		
Yes	51(68.9%)	59 (64.8%)
No	23 (31.1%)	32 (35.2%)
Total	74 (100%)	91 (100%)
Distance to the place of residence		

Less than 5 minutes by walking	12 (20.7%)	16 (19.3%)
A five-minute walk apart	15 (25.9%)	18 (21.7%)
More than 5 minutes walking distance	31 (53.4%)	49 (59.0%)
Total	58 (100%)	83 (100%)
Ever tried to get any FP method and could not in this community?		
Yes	22 (29.7%)	33 (36.3%)
No	52 (70.3%)	58 (63.7%)
Total	74 (100%)	91 (100%)
Could you get a male condom if you want?		
Yes	48 (61.5%)	57 (61.9%)
No	30 (38.5%)	35 (38.1%)
Total	78 (100%)	92 (100%)
Like to have any (more) children		
Yes	37 (47.5%)	46 (43.4%)
No	27 (34.6%)	30 (28.3%)
Undecided	14 (17.9%)	30 (28.3%)
Total	78 (100%)	106 (100%)

Length of preferred waiting period after the birth of the last child

Under six-month	4 (6.3%)	3 (3.5%)
One-year	9 (14.3%)	3 (3.5%)
One-year and 6 months	11 (17.5%)	23 (26.7%)
2 years	21 (33.3%)	30 (34.9%)
More than 2 years	18 (28.6%)	27 (31.4%)
Total	63 (100%)	86 (100%)

Will you use a contraceptive method in the future to delay or prevent becoming pregnant if you are not already doing so?

Yes	50 (66.7%)	49 (46.2%)
No	25 (33.3%)	57 (53.8%)
Total	75 (100%)	106 (100%)

Modern FP methods and reasons for choice Cont'd

Statement	EG (Ibadan) Feq (%)	CG (Osogbo) Feq (%)
Know of any customs/norms in this community that encourage/discourage the use of contraceptives in this community		
Yes	33 (44.6%)	43 (43.9%)
No		

Total	41 (55.4%)	55 (56.1%)
	74 (100%)	98 (100%)
Ever attended any reproductive health training/seminar in this community		
Yes	55 (75.3%)	56 (63.6%)
No	18 (24.7%)	32 (36.4%)
Total	73 (100%)	88 (100%)

Results from the qualitative data

The married male FGD participants in Ibadan were asked what they think will make a young man who wants to use contraception choose one method over another. They gave different views that ranged from experience and convenience. One of them said the following:

‘To me, the convenience and easy-to-get condom that I use is the reason that make me use it’. Another said that *‘easy access to the contraceptive of choice is the reason some have for choosing what they use.’* (Ibadan, Married male)

‘To me, the most effective of all the contraceptives is the use of condoms. Some still use withdrawal methods, but they are not very reliable’. (Ibadan, Married male)

Reason for choosing information on family planning

The discussants in Ibadan were asked about their views on young men accessing certain sources of information over others for contraception information. They gave different views, with some saying experience might be the reason, while others said cost also have a role to pay, while others said it is easy access and use as one of them put it:

‘Experience might be the reason some of them use their chosen method, so if you are used to a method, you may want to continue with it.’ (Married men in Ibadan)

‘To me, it is not everyone who is deaf that is aware of current FP information. Many people spend much time on phone, so media is very important as a source of information for FP among the deaf’ (Married women in Ibadan)

Discussion

In this study, a needs assessment was conducted with the view of understanding the knowledge level of MFP among the study population since it has been asserted that knowledge of MFPM is the key factor in the proper and effective use of the chosen method. Being knowledgeable helps dispel rumours, misconceptions, and fears, result in favourable attitudes toward use (Biney, 2011; Longwe, Huisman &

Smits, 2012; Mprah, 2013). Furthermore, contraceptive knowledge and use are essential determinants of access to sexual and reproductive health (SRH) information and services (Ghana Health Service & ICF Macro 2009). Furthermore, knowledge and usage of contraceptives are linked to attitudes toward and awareness about risks associated with pregnancies and sexually transmitted diseases (STDs). However, the analysis showed that the comprehensive knowledge of FP was lower (32.5%). This finding is corroborated with the findings of the qualitative study by FHI 360 (Meza, Berhane, Tenaye, Mc & Eskindir, 2017).

The fact that more participants have heard of the term modern family planning is expected. This is because there has been massive awareness creation to encourage the use of MFP among both men and women of reproductive age in Nigeria in the recent past. In the last three NDHS data, although the result shows the need to encourage more people to take up MFP, it also suggests the need to employ various strategies to encourage young people who are sexually active to use it. This finding is corroborated by that of Yimer and Modiba in Ethiopia, which shows that 97.2% of the study participants have heard of MFP (Yimer & Modiba, 2019). Although the study participants knew that there were advantages for using MFP in both study sites, the overall knowledge score of MFP among them was low. This finding agreed with the study conducted by Yimer and Modiba and that of Poku among the HIP in Ghana, which showed that the knowledge of FP was low among their study participants (Yimer & Modiba, 2019; Poku, 2008).

The result showed that more of the participants in Osogbo are more knowledgeable than those in Ibadan, which might be because more study participants are recruited from Osogbo. The results also showed that more participants agreed that the use of MFM has advantages. This is encouraging, and it is expected to translate into consistent and proper use. Media (both electronic and print) topped the list of sources of information among the participants. This finding differs from that of Kasa et al., who showed that the major sources of information were from health workers and radiologists (Kasa, Tarekegn, Embiale, 2018), and Mulatu et al., who showed that the majority of sources of information were health professionals, friends/relatives, church/mosque, and schools (Mulatu, Sintayehu, Dessie, and Deressa, 2020). Both male and female condoms topped the lists of MFPM known in the two study sites. This is at variance with a study conducted by Obalase and Joseph, which showed that the most common method heard about was pills (Obalase and Joseph, 2017) and Bakele, where injectable is the most common, and Job, which shows that the most common among respondents is withdrawal (Job, 2004; Bakele, 2020). However, the results showed that awareness of MFPM in Nigeria has grown and continues to grow over time. However, this is at variance to the Nigerian Demographic and Health Survey (2019) (NPC & ICF Macro, 2019).

Awareness and Mean Knowledge Scores on FP Methods

In this study, the level of awareness of the term MFP was high at both study sites; however, the participants' overall mean knowledge scores were still low at both sites, and the media remains their main source of information on FP issues. This finding is in agreement with previous studies in Ghana and Ethiopia, which showed that respondents' knowledge of MFPM is still low (Mprah, 2013; Yimer & Modiba, 2019). The low

knowledge of MFPM among the respondents may be due to communication barriers, lack of information, unavailability of sign language interpreters in health facilities, and non-tailored media-based dissemination of information, which are highlighted as major barriers to accessing health services (Ganle, Baatiema, Quansah, Danso-Appiah, 2020). This finding is a call for concern for the PHI because knowledge has been recognised as crucial in the quest for behavioural change in the uptake of MFP. Several studies have consistently demonstrated that knowledge of contraceptive methods is the key factor in the proper and effective use of contraceptives. Being knowledgeable can help correct rumours, misconceptions, and fears, which can result in favorable attitudes toward its use (Longwe, Huisman, & Smits, 2012; Mprah, 2013).

In this study, the level of awareness of modern FP was found to be high among the study participants. This may be a result of the comprehensive awareness campaign that has been conducted in Nigeria in the past few years on the significance of modern FP use (Zandam, Mitra, and Mitra, 2022). This intense campaign was a result of studies in some African countries that found that a lack of knowledge about FP methods and fear of side effects are issues affecting access to and uptake of FP among people with disabilities (Eide, 2015). In addition, previous studies have identified lower awareness of FP among women with disabilities in Nigeria as a major barrier to their access to reproductive health services (Zandam, Mitra, and Mitra, 2022). This result is also in agreement with the study conducted in Ethiopia, where it was discovered that about 85 % of disabled persons had heard about FP methods. The media was the most common source of information (Mekonnen, 2020).

In this study, the electronic and print media were the main sources of information on the modern FP method in the two study sites. This finding is corroborated with a study conducted in Zimbabwe (Rugoho & Maphosa, 2017) and at variance with a study conducted in Ethiopia, which showed that the most commonly reported sources of information about family planning among participants were friends/peers, followed by healthcare workers and television/radio (Yimer & Modiba, 2019). This finding reaffirms the fact that the electronic media has a positive impact on health issues and behaviour (Saraf & Balamurugan, 2018). It can bring a positive change in people's behaviour toward health issues or change the negative behaviour related to health concerns (Saraf & Balamurugan, 2018). However, studies have revealed that most of the programmes on these media were not considerate of deaf people (Ghana Health Service & ICF Macro 2009; Tejeji, Assefa, Kebede, McDowell & Tenaw, 2017). Studies conducted in Ghana, Kenya and Rwanda have highlighted awareness gaps among deaf people. They were found to have difficulty with radio messages or following workshops without sign language interpreters (Mprah, 2013; Habinshuti et al., 2017).

The male and female condoms topped the lists of modern FP methods. This is supported by a previous study among HIP in Ghana and Kenya, which showed that HIP participants were more familiar with condoms, pills, and injections (Job, 2004, Mprah, 2013). The mean modern FP knowledge scores in the two study sites were poor. Previous research has revealed that knowledge and use of contraceptives are

important indicators of access to sexual and reproductive health (SRH) information and services (Ghana Health Service & ICF Macro 2009). Many studies have also established that knowledge of methods and sources is a key factor governing the effective use of contraceptives and rectify the rumours, misconceptions and fears about the consequences of its usage (Debebe, Limenih & Biadgo, 2017; Habinshuti, Wamocho & Njoroge, 2017). Moreover, it has been established that having good knowledge reduces misconceptions and fears about contraceptives and creates positive attitudes toward use, further affirming the assertion that the more knowledge people have, the more likely they would accept and use contraceptives (Biney 2011; Longwe et al. 2012).

Perceptions of participants about family planning methods

This study intends to determine the perception of PHI on MFPM since people's perceptions may encourage or discourage couples from using MFPM. Therefore, understanding clients' perceptions of MFPM will help improve acceptance, thus reducing unintended pregnancies, induced abortion, short birth intervals, fertility rates, and maternal mortality and morbidity in the country (Dampha, Jasseh and Sey-Sawo, 2018). In this study, the majority of the participants in the two study sites had a negative perception of MFPM. This result is worrisome because it will further impede the enormous effort in encouraging the use of MFPM among adult men and women of reproductive age. This shows that there are still misconceptions, rumours and fears about condom use, which can be corrected by proper and adequate information of the advantages of condom use (Debebe, Limenih, Biadgo, 2017; Habinshuti, Wamocho and Njoroge, 2017).

Attitude of participants toward modern family planning methods

In this study, more participants in both study sites had a positive attitude about MFPMs. This result is revealing because it has been asserted that our attitude influences all our actions (Alsharari, Aziz, Taib, & Yusoff, 2018; Rikard & Banville, 2006). This result corroborates the results of a previous study conducted in Ethiopia among people with disabilities, including the deaf, which showed that 45.0% of our study participants had a good attitude about MFPM (Mekonnen, Bayleyegn, Aynalem et al., 2020). This result is also corroborated by the studies conducted in Tanzania, Turkey, and Cameroon among the disabled people; the results showed that more of the study participants had favorable attitudes about MFPM (Gürel & Yılmaz, 2018; DeBeaudrap, Mouté, Pasquier, Mac-Seing, Mukangwije & Beninguisse, 2019). However, this result is at variance with another study conducted in Ethiopia, which showed that the FGD participants mentioned that most PHI had negative attitudes toward MFPM services and did not support its use. This was attributed to the low knowledge of PHI on MFPM and prevailing unfounded rumours and misconception (Tejeji, Assefa, Kebede, McDowell & Tenaw, 2017).

Modern FP methods and reasons for choice

In this study, more participants were of the view that there are no traditional/cultural beliefs against the use of MFPM in their communities. This may be due to their limited understanding of the subject matter. There have been recent efforts to correct the prevailing myths about MFPM (NPC and ICF, 2019) in Nigeria. Several studies conducted in Nigeria among the abled bodied and the disabled people have shown that

cultural beliefs and practices influence the uptake of MFPM (Elmusharaf, Byrne, & O'Donovan, 2017; Tejeji, Assefa, Kebede, McDowell, & Tenaw, 2017).

The results of this study showed that more than half of the participants agreed that they always use MFPM to delay pregnancy and also encourage their partner to use contraceptives. This finding agreed with the study conducted by Haynes et al. (2018) among people with disabilities, including deaf people, which showed that 70% of people with disabilities who participated in the study reported contraceptive use at last intercourse (Haynes, Boulet, Fox, Carroll, Courtney-Long & Warner, 2018). This finding is also consistent with a study conducted in Ethiopia among the deaf, which showed that almost half of sexually active respondents ever used MFPM (Tessema, Bishaw and Bunare, 2015). This finding is encouraging considering the enormous challenges faced by people with disabilities in accessing reproductive health services (Haynes, Boulet, Fox, Carroll, Courtney-Long & Warner, 2018; Beyene, Munea & Fekadu, 2019; Mesfin Yesgat, Gebremeskel, Estifanous, Gizachew, Jemal, Atnafu & Nuriye, 2020). This finding also differs from a previous study, which often showed low contraceptive use among people with disabilities, including the deaf (Tessema, Bishaw & Bunare, 2015; Beyene, Munea & Fekadu, 2019). The fact that more of the participants in this study agreed that their partner supported their use of contraceptives is encouraging, as stakeholders can build on this finding that future programs targeting deaf couples should integrate partners in programmes to achieve the desired results.

More than a quarter of the participants said that they are not using any method to delay or avoid getting their partner/someone pregnant, which is corroborated by previous studies that show low contraceptive usage among the deaf (Tessema, Bishaw, & Bunare, 2015; Tejeji, Assefa, Kebede, McDowell, & Tenaw, 2017). It is noteworthy that more than a quarter of the participants in this study agreed that they have never used or tried to get any FP method. The reasons they give include that they do not want to have any (more) children. Stakeholders should reinforce the need for couples to know that contraceptives are not only meant for the prevention of pregnancy but also for the prevention of sexually transmitted infection. However, it is encouraging to know that some of the participants agreed that they think they will use a MFPM to delay or avoid getting someone pregnant at any time in the future; stakeholders and service providers should build on this. Efforts should be intensified to ensure that these participants are reinforced in their desire to use MFPM.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no conflicts of interest.

Authors' contributions

JAI and OSA conceptualized and supervised the study. JAI, OSA, and MOA participated in data analysis and interpretation. JAI, OSA, and MOA drafted the initial manuscript, and all authors contributed to the final manuscript.

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